

	<p>Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration</p>
[30/09/21]	Advancing Open Scholarship
	D5.3 – REPORT ON THE TRUST BUILDING SYSTEM DEVELOPMENT Version 1.0 – Final PUBLIC
	H2020-INFRAEOSC-2019 Grant Agreement 863420

The project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 863420.

Disclaimer- “The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the TRIPLE consortium and can in no way be taken to reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.”

This deliverable is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

Report on the Trust Building System Development

Project Acronym:	TRIPLE
Project Name:	Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration
Grant Agreement No:	863420
Start Date:	1/10/2019
End Date:	31/03/2023
Contributing WP	WP5
WP Leader:	Net7 Srl
Deliverable identifier	D5.3
Contractual Delivery Date: 09/2021	Actual Delivery Date: 30/09/2021
Nature: Report	Version: 1.0 Final
Dissemination level	PU

Revision History

Version	Created/Modifier	Comments
0.0	22/08/21 - Maxime Bouillard - Meoh ASBL	First draft
0.1	26/08/21 - Michael Köberlein - Nuromedia GmbH	Added technical descriptions
0.2	27/08/21 - Maxime Bouillard - Meoh ASBL	Added general descriptions
0.3	31/08/21 - Luca De Santis - Net7	First review
0.4	07/09/21 - Maxime Bouillard - Meoh ASBL	Corrections
0.5	09/09/21 - Giulio Andreini - Net7	Added frontend mock-ups
0.6	22/09/21 - Francesca Di Donato - CNR	Second review
0.7	27/09/21 - Maxime Bouillard - Meoh ASBL	Final revision
1.0	30/09/21 - Maxime Bouillard - Meoh ASBL	Sent to coordinators

Table of Contents

1. DESCRIPTION OF THE SERVICE	7
1.1 The Trust Building System (TBS) as one of the innovative services of GoTriple	7
1.2 Added value of the service to the GoTriple platform	7
2. DESCRIPTION OF THE WORK DONE IN GOTRIPLE	8
2.1 Implementing End-Users Co-Design	8
2.1.1 Context and methodology	8
2.1.2 Recommendations from D3.3	9
2.2 Software development plan for the TBS	15
2.3 TBS Functionalities	16
3. TBS INTEGRATION IN GOTRIPLE	19
3.1 Context and challenges	19
3.1.1 User management	19
3.1.2 Notifications	20
3.2 Software architecture	21
3.3 Frontend	24
3.3.1 TBS integration in the GoTriple homepage	24
3.3.2 TBS integration in the user notification stream	26
3.3.3 TBS integration in the user profile	28
3.3.4 The Web version of the TBS	28
4. NEXT STEPS	31
5. ANNEXES	32
5.1 TBS User Terms	32
5.2 TBS Privacy Policy	41
5.3 TBS Community Guidelines	46
5.4 TBS User Profiles	50
6. REFERENCES	51

List of Figures

<i>Figure 1. Technical diagram of the TBS in the GoTriple platform.</i>	22
<i>Figure 2. Innovative services in TRIPLE and their level of integration (source: D6.2).</i>	24
<i>Figure 3. TBS main metric in the GoTriple Homepage.</i>	25
<i>Figure 4. TBS notifications in the user notifications stream.</i>	26
<i>Figure 5. TBS button in GoTriple User Profiles.</i>	28
<i>Figure 6. TBS screenshot of linking accounts with the GoTriple platform.</i>	29
<i>Figure 7. TBS screenshot of a Post details page.</i>	29
<i>Figure 8. Meoh App screenshot of a user Profile page.</i>	30
<i>Figure 9. Meoh App screenshot of the Newsfeed page.</i>	30
<i>Figure 10. Meoh App screenshot of a Post details page.</i>	30

List of Tables

<i>Table 1. Summary of recommendations from D3.3.</i>	9
<i>Table 2. Implemented functionalities in the Web version of the TBS.</i>	16
<i>Table 3. TBS notifications for the GoTriple interface.</i>	27
<i>Table 4. Summary of recommendations from workshop #4 in Task 3.3.</i>	50

Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
APNS	Apple Push Notification Service
B2B	Business-to-Business
B2C	Business-to-Consumer
DoW	Description of Work
EGI	European Grid Infrastructure
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FCM	Firebase Cloud Messaging
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GoTriple	TRIPLE online platform available at gotriple.eu
IaaS	Infrastructure-as-a-Service
ID	Identification
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JWT	JSON Web Token
OAuth	Open Authorization
OPERAS	Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social sciences and humanities
OPERAS-P	Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social sciences and humanities - Infrastructure
PHP	Hypertext Preprocessor
RI	Research Infrastructure
SIG	Special interest Group
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
TBS	Trust Building System
TRIPLE	Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration
UI	User Interface
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
UX	User Experience

Definition

“Trust is understood as a relational attribute between social actors (interpersonal trust) where trusting actors willingly put themselves in a position of vulnerability in order to achieve a positive outcome.”¹

DRAFT

¹ Our definition of trust is derived from Becker, M. & Bodó, B. (2021). Trust in blockchain-based systems. *Internet Policy Review*, 10(2). <https://doi.org/10.14763/2021.2.1555>

Publishable Summary

We present here the work done in Task T5.3, dedicated to the development of the Trust Building System (TBS) and its integration in the GoTriple platform. The TBS is one of the “social engines” and one of the innovative services of the GoTriple platform. Its purpose is to help Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) researchers connect to reliable partners within and outside the SSH community. It furthers the main objective of GoTriple which is to dramatically improve the impact of SSH thanks to an enhanced visibility and accessibility of its research. The TBS offers unique features that can help SSH researchers enhance potential synergies in multistakeholder environments where horizontal cooperation is required. As such, it increases GoTriple’s appeal notably thanks to the focus on trust that distinguishes this service from other social networks.

This document starts by describing the characteristics of the TBS, its added value, and its positioning in the context of the TRIPLE project. Next, it reports on the work done in T5.3 with the implementation of functionalities elicited by the end-user co-design research in Task T3.3. The document then explores the technical strategy to overcome integration challenges along with the software architecture and the chosen front-end integration points. Finally, it outlines the diverse activities that will need to be carried out in the next period of the TRIPLE project with the identification of exploitation models and sustainability strategies.

DRAFT

1. DESCRIPTION OF THE SERVICE

1.1 The Trust Building System (TBS) as one of the innovative services of GoTriple

In the present report we provide the foundation for one of the five innovative services of the GoTriple platform², which also include the integration of third-party applications such as a Crowdfunding Tool (Task 5.1), a Recommender System (Task 5.2), a Visualisation and Discovery System (Tasks 5.4 and 5.6), and an Open Annotation Tool (Task 5.5). The TBS is a referral system meant to help SSH researchers discover and connect to reliable partners and is one of the “social engines” of the GoTriple platform. Examples include finding the right coordinator for Horizon Europe consortia; finding the right experts such as PhD students or policy makers; or connecting to end-users for them to participate in and benefit from research projects.

Unfettered connectivity did not systematically correlate with an increase in online cooperation. Fueled by user data collection, social technologies provide systematic incentives to increase the exposure of people and content at the expense of meaning; and therefore of trust and potential for collaboration. As the offline and online worlds are now merging with one another at unprecedented levels, the TBS aims to take an approach to social networking where trusted relationships are at the core of the user experience.

To achieve the promise of an “end-to-end” trust at scale, the TBS is built on a “few-to-few” social architecture that embeds those qualitative relationships observed in cohesive social clusters in a continuum of trust. This approach translates as private³ human-sized networks⁴, where new social connections are always triangulated by trusted intermediaries, in which members support each other with reciprocal favours, and where all users have vested interests in the behaviors of their peers as their interactions can affect their own perceived credibility and trustworthiness⁵.

1.2 Added value of the service to the GoTriple platform

The main objective of GoTriple is to dramatically improve the impact of SSH research thanks to an enhancement of its visibility and accessibility. It offers a discovery solution based on three different kinds of objects: publications (and datasets), profiles, and projects. Aimed at enabling effective networking, relevant matchmaking, and strong partnerships, the TBS will operate as a referral network to help SSH researchers develop and maintain sufficient levels of trust with

² <https://www.gotriple.eu/>

³ The service is invite-only.

⁴ Limited to a maximum of 150 people (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dunbar%27s_number).

⁵ The TBS is based on the trust architecture developed by Meoh ASBL (see Ref. 1).

other stakeholders. The purpose is to enable them reach viable thresholds of cooperation and create synergies within, across and beyond the SSH community.

While some functionalities of the TBS overlap with some of those of the GoTriple platform, we recognise that the Trust Building System offers unique features that can help SSH researchers enhance potential synergies in multistakeholder environments where horizontal cooperation is required. As such, it can increase GoTriple's appeal notably thanks to the focus on trust that distinguishes this service from other social networks and by redirecting its own user base to the GoTriple platform.

2. DESCRIPTION OF THE WORK DONE IN GOTRIPLE

2.1 Implementing End-Users Co-Design

The main goal of Work Package 5 is the design, development, and integration of innovative applications and tools that will augment GoTriple's core services. These federated applications and tools will deliver additional services for SSH researchers and other TRIPLE stakeholders. Our iterative approach used advanced prototypes to conduct research with end-users co-designing the system. The output of the co-design component in Task 3.3 "Trust Building System User Design Research" directly informs its implementation in Task 5.3 "Trust Building System Development and Integration in the GoTriple discovery platform." As part of this work, there has been the development of Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) that connect the service with the GoTriple platform, the implementation of the trust architecture developed by Meoh and the delivery of end-user interfaces.

2.1.1 Context and methodology

By using advanced prototypes and adopting an iterative approach, research was conducted with end-users in Task 3.1 to co-design the system. We conducted a series of eight workshops: three theoretical ones, from which we collected rich information on the expected basic guiding principles for a TBS; and five practical ones from which we gathered rich information on the concrete user experience as well as on what features to keep, what to exclude, and what to improve.

In those workshops, ideas were discussed, assumptions were challenged, mock-ups were designed or further improved for each stage of the user experience thanks to the valuable input of end-users. This series of workshops helped us gain deeper insights into the purpose, guiding principles and values of such a system, and it informed a first draft of the community guidelines underlining its ethics. It also gave us recommendations and outputs on functionalities, such as the inviting or posting processes, and for the design of the system's main pages like users profiles and the newsfeed. The results were further processed to inform and improve the TBS designs for the TRIPLE Deliverable 5.3 "Development and Integration of a Trust Building System" whose purpose is to implement the D3.3 recommendations.

Additionally, a survey was circulated among consortium members to get a better understanding of their needs when it comes to reaching out to new partners. The survey complemented the workshops with a broader perspective providing fundamental information on how to shape the final version of the system. It provides some insights about the preferred use of the system, the preferred ways to reach out to new potential partners, and the perceived strengths and weaknesses of the offered functionalities. As such, it also contributes directly to D.5.3.

2.1.2 Recommendations from D3.3

We provide here a summary of recommendations from D3.3 “Report on the Trust Building System User Design Research.” Those recommendations are wishes that have been confronted against a technological and budgetary check prior to implementation. For the complete list of end-user recommendations, please see Appendix 2 of deliverable D3.3 “End-User Co-Design Research.”

TABLE 1. SUMMARY OF RECOMMENDATIONS FROM D3.3.

Ref.	Recommendations	Comments and suggested implementation
R.0.1	Provide academic users with a social network to better connect and work within, across, and beyond their own fields of expertise and disciplines.	Accepted: conform to Meoh’s trust architecture (See Ref. 1).
R.0.2	Enable users to find academics/key researchers within an area of expertise.	Rejected/postponed for budgetary concerns.
R.0.3	Enable users to view mutual acquaintances.	Accepted: 1. Click on "Profile" of contact. 2. Click on the "Mutual" icon on the user profile.
R.0.4	Enable users to send invitations to an event.	Rejected/postponed for budgetary concerns.
R.0.5	Enable users to find out what type of collaboration other researchers are interested in.	Rejected/postponed for budgetary concerns.
R.0.6	Enable users to search for a native English speaker in their academic	Rejected/postponed for budgetary concerns.

	area.	
R.0.7	Enable users to view Special interest Groups (SIG).	Accepted: 1. Click on the "Communities" icon on the navigation bar. 2. Click on the selected "Community."
R.0.8	Enable users to connect with others via the SIG.	Accepted: 1. Click on the "3 dots" menu icon of a community conversation page. 2. Click on "Add me to your network."
R.0.9	Enable users to view posts in the SIG.	Accepted: 1. Posts can be forwarded to a community conversation page. 2. Click on "Chat posts" in the "3 dots" menu icon of a community conversation page.
R.0.10	Search "Communities of Practice" by topic or project.	Rejected/postponed for budgetary concerns.
R.0.11	Enable searches to find and follow relevant projects and people rather than just posts.	Rejected/postponed for budgetary concerns.
R.0.12	Enable introductions to friends, colleagues, and trusted contacts.	Accepted: 1. Click on "Profile" of contact. 2. Click on the "Introduce" icon on the profile. 3. Click on the "Add contact" icon and click on the "Done" button. 4. Click on the "Introduce" button.
R.0.13	Create an "Introduce" function between people who don't know each other but who could help each other via a trusted intermediary. An alert would be prompted in case users are already connected.	Accepted: same as R.0.12.
R.0.14	Address concerns regarding Covid-19's effect on work life.	Addressed in the TBS survey (see D3.3 section 4 TBS Survey on SSH Urgent and

		Pressing Needs).
R.0.15	Increase the chances of requests to be solved by making them visible to second degree connections through the “featured peers.”	Accepted: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click on the "My network" icon on the navigation bar. 2. Click on the toggle icon to display “Featured peers.”
R.0.16	Make TBS pages easy to understand as too many menus and services may overwhelm users. Make the TBS desktop and mobile friendly.	Accepted: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. User co-design workshops helped us simplify our designs. 2. The TBS is made on a responsive design.
R.0.17	Consider chat and emails as preferred communication tools, potentially audio recording too.	Accepted: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Encrypted chat has been set up in the mobile prototype. 2. Audio recording has been set up in the mobile prototype but might not be a good fit for the desktop version of the TBS.
R.1.1	Create a user-friendly system offering easy communication between SSH researchers and other stakeholders such as Policy Makers and Civil Society.	Accepted: same as R.0.1.
R.1.2	Develop a service that encourages informal interactions in order to enhance trust.	Accepted: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Personal recommendations. 2. Username instead of real name. 3. Soft skills and informal information on user profiles (see Annex 6.4 TBS User Profile).
R.1.3	Make the system mobile-friendly.	Accepted: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Responsive design. 2. Interoperable with the prototype designed for mobile devices (Android and iOS).
R.1.4	Focus on existing trusted relationships and expand from there.	Accepted: same as R.0.1.

R.2.1	Reflect the values of Trust, Diversity, Sustainability, Accountability, Inclusivity, and Transparency in the design of the TBS.	Accepted: see Annex 6.3 TBS Community Guidelines.
R.2.2	Limit personal networks to one hundred and fifty participants.	Accepted: same as R.0.1.
R.2.3	Curate the network with an invite-only system and with the triangulation of new introductions by trusted intermediaries.	Accepted: same as R.0.1.
R.2.4	Encourage users to engage in informal interactions.	Accepted: same as R.0.1.
R.2.5	Bind TBS users with Community Guidelines that reflect the core Values and Principles of the TBS.	Accepted: see Annex 6.3 TBS Community Guidelines.
R.2.6	Reflect sustainability in the technological and energy consumption choices of the platform.	Accepted: align on best practices and state of the art.
R.3.1	Create a newsfeed for people to display their requests and for others to help solve them.	Accepted: feature available by clicking on the "My newsfeed" icon on the navigation bar.
R.3.2	Set up a process, based on a community of practice, where people's behaviour could affect the reputation of their peers.	Accepted: same as R.0.1.
R.3.3	Provide sufficient information for users to assess the personality of their peers.	Accepted: see Annex 6.4 TBS User Profile.
R.3.4	Offer social bridges to find reliable partners through human referral.	Accepted: same as R.0.1.
R.3.5	Enable the possibility to forward published requests to trusted contacts who could potentially help solve them because they would have the	Accepted: 1. Click on the "My newsfeed" icon on the navigation bar.

	expertise or would know someone who would have the required expertise.	2. Click on the “Forward” icon on the post summary or detail page.
R.3.6	Create Special Interest Groups to form communities of practices that could discuss and share ideas.	Accepted: 1. Click on the “Plus” button. 2. Click on the “Create community” button. 3. Add relevant information and click “Create.”
R.3.7	Curate the network through private invitations.	Accepted: 1. Click on the “Plus” button. 2. Click on the “Invite” button. 3. Choose the preferred media and click “Send.”
R.3.8	Provide gamifications mechanics such as awards with a set of incentives to make them valuable.	Accepted: - For users: 1. Click on a user “Profile” page. 2. Click on the “Award” icon. 3. Click on the “Award” button. - For content: 1. Click on a publication. 2. Click the “Award” icon next to a comment. 3. Click on the “Award” button.
R.4.1	Implement or adapt the suggested TBS cooperation profile.	Accepted: see Annex 6.4 TBS User Profile.
R.5.1	Implement the Community Guidelines, bound to evolve over time and to adapt to the TBS changes.	Accepted: see Annex 6.3 TBS Community Guidelines.
R.6.1	Create a newsfeed showing the activity of the trusted network.	Accepted: same as R.3.1.
R.6.2	Skip the audio messaging functionality in the desktop version of the system.	Suggestion accepted.
R.6.3	Embed customer support e.g. videos explaining the user journey, features,	Accepted: Tips and FAQs in TBS version 1, others in version 2.

	or a chat bot.	
R.6.4	Make sure that the system gains stability.	Suggestion accepted.
R.6.5	Put the focus on the Trusted Network and on the Newsfeed pages for a greater user experience.	Suggestion accepted.
R.6.6	Test the TBS over a longer period of time.	Suggestion accepted.
R.7.1	Make the newsfeed the default landing page.	Suggestion accepted.
R.7.2	Enable comments editing and improve the visibility of the “comment, forward, repost, and bookmark” icons.	Suggestion accepted.
R.7.3	Place newest activities on top of the newsfeed stream.	Suggestion accepted.
R.7.4	Provide tutorials to explain functionalities e.g. short explanatory videos.	Accepted: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Suggestion accepted for videos, in the making. 2. TIPs displayed when relevant. 3. FAQs in the main menu.
R.7.5	Insert the Chat in the main “Plus” button.”	Postponed until use cases have been better defined.
R.7.6	Enable video calls.	Rejected/postponed for technical and budgetary concerns.
R.7.7	Provide additional information on people who are not yet in one’s network to add some human touch and to better grasp those populating the networks of their trusted peers.	Accepted: see Annex 6.4 TBS User Profile.
R.7.8	Import contacts from other social media accounts.	Accepted: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. EGI check-in enabled (not yet implemented but planned). 2. Other social media accounts (planned for version 2).

R.7.9	Indicate the amount of mutual contacts between users.	Suggestion accepted.
R.7.10	Trigger a system alert if users try to introduce people who are already connected with each other.	Suggestion accepted.
R.8.1	See suggested way to integrate the TBS into the GoTriple Discovery Platform.	Accepted: see Section 4. TBS Integration into GoTriple.

2.2 Software development plan for the TBS

This section provides a simplified description of the development plan of the TBS which has been gradually expanded during the work process between M12 and to this day (M24). The TBS is being developed as a Web frontend and is integrated in the interface of the GoTriple platform. It shares the same backend architecture as the Meoh App⁶ which has been used as a prototyping device for the co-design workshops in Task 3.3.

1. Establishing first API connection

Since the TBS does not have an independent backend architecture and shares the one provided by the Meoh App, the first step was to establish a general API connection to test if all necessary API Endpoints were available. This was done through individual test scenarios and the implementation of first features like logging in and reading profile information and posts.

2. Test and check the availability of API Endpoints

The second step was the major topic for most of the development phase. Since the TBS followed the development of the Meoh App, the focus laid on realizing all existing features of the Meoh app in the TBS Web Frontend. After the reading of the data through the API connection was confirmed, writing data e.g. “publishing posts” or “updating profile” information was the next logical step. From this, all major features and actions were implemented incrementally. Below is a list of all major feature components in chronological order of implementation.

- Implementation of registering and logging in.
- Displaying profile information of users and contacts.
- Making it possible to update profile information through the TBS Web frontend.
- Displaying posts by other contacts.

⁶ <https://www.meoh.io/app>

- Implementing posting, sharing and editing posts.
- Implementing chat and group chat functions.

3. Bringing the TBS up to date with the prototype

During the development of the TBS, the Meoh App was adapted to take end-users input into account and to test out new functionalities during the co-design workshops. After implementing most of the core features, the TBS was then brought up to date to reflect the same features as the Meoh App. This includes features such as a dashboard compiling statistics about users' personal networks as well as the possibility to award other users for their positive contributions.

4. Quality Assurance and Bug Fixing

The development phase of the TBS is currently at this step right now (M 24). The current state of the frontend is still being tested and improved. Component testing of different areas of the platform and the fixing of bugs is also still a main part of the current development cycles. The same goes for redesigning specific areas of the frontend which proved to be inadequate after longer periods of testing.

2.3 TBS Functionalities

The following are the existing prototype functionalities developed for mobile devices (Android and iOS⁷) that were eligible to be implemented in the Web version of the TBS.

TABLE 2. IMPLEMENTED FUNCTIONALITIES IN THE WEB VERSION OF THE TBS.

Prototype functionalities	Accepted functionalities in the TBS
Drop down menu <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. My received invitations 2. My notifications 3. My favourites 4. My coins 5. My settings 6. Log out 7. About 	Drop down menu <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. My received invitations 2. My notifications 3. My favourites 4. My coins 5. Missing API Endpoint - Not available in the web version 6. Log out 7. About

⁷ <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.luezoid.meoh>
<https://apps.apple.com/us/app/id1466786850>

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. FAQs 9. Donate 10. Community guidelines 11. Privacy policy 12. User terms 13. Feedback 14. Bug report 15. Build information 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. FAQs 9. Donate 10. Community guidelines 11. Privacy policy 12. User terms 13. Feedback 14. Bug report 15. Missing API Endpoint- Not available in the web version
<p>Main sections</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. My newsfeed 2. My network (trusted/featured) 3. My communities 4. My chats 5. My profile 6. My dashboard 7. My awards 	<p>Main sections</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. My newsfeed 2. My network (trusted/featured) 3. My communities 4. My chats 5. My profile 6. My dashboard 7. My awards
<p>User actions</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Register 2. Login 3. Recover password 4. Link email address 5. Invite user 6. Accept/reject invite 7. Introduce user 8. Award user 9. Report content 10. Report user 11. Block user 12. Edit profile 13. Publish post 	<p>User actions</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Register 2. Login 3. Recover password 4. Link email address 5. Invite user 6. Accept/reject invite 7. Introduce user 8. Award user 9. Report content 10. Report user 11. Block user 12. Edit profile 13. Publish post

14. Comment on post	14. Comment on post
15. Repost	15. Repost
16. Forward post	16. Forward post
17. Bookmark post	17. Bookmark post
18. Edit post	18. Edit post
19. Delete post	19. Delete post
20. Send message	20. Send message
21. Pin/unpin message	21. Pin/unpin message
22. Reply to message	22. Reply to message
23. Forward message	23. Forward message
24. Delete message	24. Delete message
25. Send attachment	25. Send attachment
26. Record audio	26. Record audio
27. Edit audio	27. Edit audio
28. Delete audio	28. Missing API Endpoint - Not available in the web version
29. Create community	29. Create community
30. Edit community	30. Edit community
31. Leave community	31. Leave community
32. Report conversation	32. Report conversation
33. Add community members	33. Add community members
34. Add community admins	34. Add community admins
35. Add me to your network	35. Add me to your network
36. Provide feedback	36. Provide feedback
37. Mute/unmute notifications	37. Missing API Endpoint - Not available in the web version
38. Deactivate/reactivate account	38. Deactivate/reactivate account
39. Delete account	39. Delete account
40. Erase user data	40. Erase user data

3. TBS INTEGRATION IN GOTRIPLE

3.1 Context and challenges

Some innovative services that we can define as “Federated Services,” in particular the Trust Building System (T5.3), the Open Annotation Tool Pundit (T5.5), and possibly some third party applications still to be identified (T5.1), will have an autonomous policy for user management respect to GoTriple as their users might not know about GoTriple and vice versa. First of all, those innovative services can have an existing user base, unaware of GoTriple. Second, even if some might already have integrated, or plan to integrate the EGI AAI Check-In service for user registration and authentication⁸, their users might not be concerned by GoTriple. Those innovative services might also have other registration or authentication options, such as Google or Facebook OAuth⁹. Specific integration strategies are therefore necessary, since a TRIPLE Innovative Service cannot be independent from GoTriple as explicitly mentioned in the project’s DoW¹⁰. We define in the following sections the minimum integration requirements that any federated service must satisfy to ensure a smooth integration with GoTriple.

3.1.1 User management

User registration, as well as the Edit Profile interface in GoTriple, will include the following options for linking existing TBS accounts with GoTriple Profiles. By selecting one of the “linking existing account” options, the user will be redirected to a special page implemented on the Federated Service side (TBS) to perform the system’s authentication. In addition, a reference to the GoTriple user identification (ID) must be passed to these services. If the authentication is successful, the federated service - The TBS in the present case - must store the GoTriple user ID in the local user profile and the user returns to the GoTriple registration/profile editing page from where the process started. Also the federated service user ID must be passed to GoTriple and stored in the user profile.

The process that we just described, involves the following implementations:

- In work package 4 (WP4)
 - Changes to the GoTriple user registration interfaces.
 - Changes to the GoTriple User Profile data model and editing interfaces, including the possibility for the user to explicitly remove the connection with a Federated Service.
- In the Federated Service (TBS)

⁸ <https://wiki.egi.eu/wiki/AAI>

⁹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/OAuth>

¹⁰ From the WP5 description of the DoW: “The main goal of WP5 is the design, development and integration of innovative applications and tools that are not part of the core of the TRIPLE platform (the core is part of WP 4). These applications and tools will work on top of this core and deliver additional fundamental services for SSH researchers and other TRIPLE stakeholders”.

- Develop a special authentication page to link the user account to the GoTriple profile.
- Make changes in the user profile to allow users to delete their connection with GoTriple.

We decided to implement a secure, simple, yet robust way to connect the IDs/accounts. Looking at the user's ID journey:

1. From GoTriple to the External Service:
 - a. The user clicks a link that contains the GoTriple user ID, which is encrypted and opens a new tab or page on the External Service.
 - b. The External Service authenticates the user, unless already authenticated at a prior stage.
 - c. It shows a confirmation message: "Do you want to connect your account to GoTriple?"
 - d. If users accept, their GoTriple user ID is stored into the user's profile in the External Service.
2. From the External Service to GoTriple:
 - a. When the user clicks on the "Return to GoTriple" button, a redirection must be issued to a specific GoTriple Uniform Resource Locator (URL). This step can be done automatically. The redirection URL can have as parameters the state of the reconciliation (state=ok/nok) and an identification of the external service (from=tbs).
 - b. GoTriple saves on the user profile the fact that the connection with that specific External Service has been successful (if the state is ok).

3.1.2 Notifications

GoTriple plans to visualise "notifications" of important events (e.g. new publication, new recommended resource) in the "MyGoTriple" Webpage. This relates also to the TBS. GoTriple will not make any assumption about the "semantics" of these notifications: it will be the responsibility of the federated services to notify GoTriple with "messages" to be shown in the "MyGoTriple" Webpage.

When specific events occur that require a user notification, the TBS will check if the user is also a GoTriple user. In this case, it will send a message to a notification endpoint implemented in GoTriple and will store in its repository these notifications - at least for a certain amount of time that remains to be defined. The homepage for logged in users also includes a "What's new" area where some blocks display metrics of relevant events and activities related to the user. By storing the notifications on the GoTriple side it will be possible to easily calculate these metrics and to show the notifications list, without any dependencies with the TBS.

This involves the following implementations:

- In WP4:
 - Notification endpoint. In this way, any future third party applications integrated in GoTriple, including the Messaging service, will be able to send notifications to be shown in the MyGoTriple page.
 - A mechanism to delete notifications after a certain time (e.g. older than thirty days).
- In the Federated Service (TBS)
 - Sending meaningful notifications to the GoTriple endpoint after having checked if the user belongs to the GoTriple community.

3.2 Software architecture

No independent backend was developed as part of the TBS development. Instead, the backend of the TBS predecessor is used via an API. The predecessor of TBS is an application for iOS and Android called the Meoh app. This is a former prototype that was further developed into a full app product. However, due to its app character, it can only be used on smartphones and this architecture also prevents a link to GoTriple. The TBS as a responsive web platform serves as a further development and link to GoTriple. The Meoh app and the associated backend were developed outside the Triple project. Nevertheless, here a brief description of the backend which is used by TBS via an API follows. The following diagram shows the networked architecture of the Meoh app and its individual components.

FIGURE 1. Technical diagram of the TBS in the GoTriple platform.

User management is managed through a PHP web application based on the MySQL database¹¹. The MySQL relational database serves as a backbone of the platform. The platform runs on a Linux environment, Debian¹², where all the components of the backend are developed in PHP¹³ and a MySQL database technology is used to store the data. The backend of the MEOH architecture implements Representational State Transfer (REST) APIs¹⁴ providing and accepting data in the JSON format¹⁵. A file system is used for the storage of images and audio files which

¹¹ <https://www.mysql.com/>

¹² <https://www.debian.org/>

¹³ <https://www.php.net/>

¹⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Representational_state_transfer

¹⁵ <https://www.json.org/json-en.html>

may be uploaded to the system. All these data and files are secured through AES (Advanced Encryption Standard) encryption¹⁶. AES is a symmetric encryption method and was developed by Vincent Rijmen and Joan Daemen and is known as the Rijndael algorithm¹⁷. AES is based on block cipher and is the successor of Data Encryption Standard (DES)¹⁸. Nowadays, it is used as a standard method in many areas of data transmission. AES encryption being a symmetric method, the same key is used for both encryption and decryption.

Since the development of a stand-alone architecture for communication control is extremely complex and costly, this area was developed with the help of an external service. Communication via chat, chat groups (called “communities” in the TBS), and notifications are handled using the PubNub service¹⁹. This service is a real time communication platform and a real time Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS)²⁰. PubNub's primary product is a real time publish and subscribe messaging API²¹ built on their global data stream network which is made up of a replicated network. Notification services such as APNS²² and FCM²³ will not be discussed further here, as both are only relevant for communication with the two application versions of the Meoh App but not relevant for the TBS. In the TBS, corresponding notifications are only displayed on the platform itself.

DRAFT

¹⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Advanced_Encryption_Standard

¹⁷ Daemen J., Rijmen V. (2020) Design Philosophy. In: The Design of Rijndael. Information Security and Cryptography. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-60769-5_5

¹⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Data_Encryption_Standard

¹⁹ <https://www.pubnub.com/>

²⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Infrastructure_as_a_service

²¹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/API>

²² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Apple_Push_Notification_service

²³ <https://firebase.google.com/docs/cloud-messaging>

3.3 Frontend

The diagram below shows how the TBS is positioned in regard to the other software systems developed in TRIPLE. In particular, the TBS is an autonomous platform - in terms of users and its onboarding process - in respect to the GoTriple platform. Therefore, the integration of these two platforms must be based on a federation paradigm. The following are the strategies we identified to perform this integration.

Following end-users recommendations elicited during the co-design workshops and internal discussions with partners to assess technical and budgetary feasibility, we identified three main points of integration for the first version of the TBS within the GoTriple frontend:

1. The GoTriple homepage
2. The registered user's notification stream
3. The registered user's profile page

Figure 2. Innovative services in TRIPLE and their level of integration (source: D6.2).

3.3.1 TBS integration in the GoTriple homepage

The homepage will be available to any users - registered and non registered - visiting the GoTriple website. A “What’s new” section will display a selected few metrics from the platform’s various services including from its innovative services such as the TBS. This section is further divided into two subsections: “What’s new for you on GoTriple in the last seven days,” and “GoTriple updates in the last seven days.”

The first subsection displays the number of:

- New messages
- Recommended resources

- Pundit notifications
- TBS users

After considering the various metrics listed below, the number of new TBS users (last seven days) appears to be the most relevant metric to be initially displayed on the GoTriple homepage.

- Number of new registered users (highlighted in Figure 3)
- Number of posts/publications
- Number of recent activity (comments, reposts, forwards, bookmarks, awards)
- Number of communities (chat groups)
- Number of introductions

FIGURE 3. Main TBS metric in the GoTriple Homepage (see the red box highlight).

3.3.2 TBS integration in the user notification stream

A notification stream will be available to the registered users of GoTriple and will display notifications (see figure 3) from various GoTriple services including those of the TBS (listed below in Table 3).

The screenshot shows the GoTriple user interface for Massimiliano Spinosa. The notification stream, titled "What's new", contains the following items:

- 8 Sep 2021 - 9:45: **Steve Horowitz has commented on your post**. [Go to the post](#)
- 6 Sep 2021 - 15:31: **Alan Brinkmann has replied to your message.** [See reply](#)
- 4 Sep 2021 - 11:43: **Leonardo Vitali has replied to your comment**. [Go to the post](#)
- 4 Sep 2021 - 9:12: **Martin Cooper introduced you to David McLahan**. [Join the conversation](#)
- 2 Sep 2021 - 7:45: **Philippe Gautret likes your Pundit annotation on "Femicide as act and process: a geography of..."**. [See annotation](#)
- 1 Sep 2021 - 12:45: **Leonardo Vitali featured you!**. [See it on the TBS](#)
- 24 Ago 2021 - 7:00: **Eric Thomson sent you a message.** [See Message](#)

A red box highlights the notifications from the TBS (Trust Building System), which are the first six items in the stream.

FIGURE 4. TBS notifications in the user notifications stream (see the red box highlight).

Here is the list of chosen notifications at this time (M24) that will be pulled from the TBS and shown in the GoTriple interface.

Table 3. TBS notifications for the GoTriple interface.

Source	Name	Description	UI
TBS	You received an invitation	A user has invited you	<USERNAME> has sent you an invite. Go to the invite! <DATE>
TBS	Your invitation has been accepted	A user has accepted your invitation	<USERNAME> has accepted your invitation! <DATE>
TBS	Your post has been commented	A user has commented your post	<USERNAME> has commented on your post. Go to the post! <DATE>
TBS	Your post has been reposted	A user has reposted your post	<USERNAME> has reposted your post. Go to the post! <DATE>
TBS	Your post has been forwarded	A user has forwarded your post	<USERNAME> has forwarded your post. Go to the post! <DATE>
TBS	Your post has been bookmarked	A user has bookmarked your post	<USERNAME> has bookmarked your post. Go to the post! <DATE>
TBS	You have a reply to your comment	A user has been replying to your comment	<USERNAME> has replied to your comment. Go to the post! <DATE>
TBS	You have been featured	A user has been featuring you	<USERNAME> featured you! <DATE>
TBS	You have been awarded	A user has been awarding you	<USERNAME> awarded you! Go to your awards! <DATE>
TBS	You have been introduced	A user has been introducing you	<USERNAME> introduced you to <USERNAME>. Join the conversation! <DATE>

3.3.3 TBS integration in the user profile

Finally, a TBS button will be integrated in the registered users' profiles and will provide a direct link to the TBS by opening a new browser tab. The profile settings in the TBS are opened. What still needs to be implemented in the profile settings is a button such as "Link TBS Account to GoTriple" which connects the two accounts. In this way TBS notifications can be communicated to GoTriple and displayed there in the indicated places.

FIGURE 5. TBS button in GoTriple User Profiles (see the red box highlight in the top right corner).

3.3.4 The Web version of the TBS

We present below the first screenshots of the Web version of the TBS developed by Nuromedia in TRIPLE. The first one shows the linking between the Meoh App users accounts and the GoTriple ones as the users management proved to be the biggest challenge to overcome while integrating the TBS in the GoTriple platform. The second one shows a typical Post details page where users can display their requests to the attention of their trusted contacts and their peers. While the TBS is fully connected to the Meoh App, its UI is still in development and will evolve to provide a seamless experience between the Web and mobile versions of the TBS.

Figure 6. TBS screenshot of linking a TBS account with the GoTriple platform.

Figure 7. TBS screenshot of a Post details page.

The TBS in its Web version and the Meoh App are part of the same user experience: while the former is being integrated in the GoTriple platform and can be used via a Web browser, its users can at any time fire up their mobile app to check what's happening in their circles of trusted connections and share their experiences with them "on the go." The images below show the Meoh app as used during the co-design workshops with end-users.

Figure 8. Meoh app screenshot of a user Profile page.

Figure 9. Meoh app screenshot of the Newsfeed page.

Figure 10. Meoh app screenshot of a Post details page.

4. NEXT STEPS

The development of the TBS core components has been accomplished in the first 24 months of the project while the development team is completing the integration with GoTriple, following the methodology described herein. In the remaining project time, support will be provided to the GoTriple development team for the improvement of the user interface, for the maintenance of the system, for bug fixing, and for security updates. We will also assess with consortium partners how Triple core and its external services might exchange (personal) data for research purposes and update our user terms and privacy policies accordingly. There is, however, no prefixed planning for bringing additional features to the TBS at this stage. We will first test the beta version of the system with early adopters for a longer period of time and gather relevant usage data. Thanks to an internal dashboard providing accurate metrics, through surveys, and through embedded feedback forms we will detect and analyse the most successful and also the less promising functionalities. Based on those results, we will adapt the TBS in order to improve the user experience and to zero in on its unique selling point in order to make it fit for the market.

Avenues of exploration have already been elicited as being desirable by end-users in our co-design workshops. Some haven't been implemented in the TBS yet for budgetary concerns. This is the case of specific cooperation profiles dedicated to consortium building in the frame of EU funded projects. Others, like the integration of social logins have been postponed after we gain the necessary understandings and the deeper insights in how the system will perform though it could lead to wider user adoption. In this direction, integrating the service more tightly within the European ecosystem such as within the EOSC marketplace is also under consideration. To ensure a sustainable revenue model for the TBS, we will first offer the TBS free of charge in order to test out the various functionalities, to consolidate the user experience, and to grow the user base at a healthy pace. From there, we could evolve toward a paid model that could be threefold:

1. A Business-to-Consumer part (B2C) where end-users access premium functionalities by subscribing to a paid plan for a monthly fee or a yearly subscription.
2. A Business-to-Business part (B2B) where business partners purchase a monthly, yearly or pluriannual licence for providing the TBS service to its members.
3. An "Add-ons" part where third-parties develop specific functionalities with a revenue distribution between the TBS team and its commercial partners.

These B2B and B2C opportunities are expected to emerge with the growth of the GoTriple and TBS user base. To help it grow, we will consolidate an online marketing plan for community building in collaboration with the TRIPLE communication team. Moreover, we will actively target potential TBS users and advertise the service and its benefits in all relevant offline and online events. We will also analyse usage data and share results in a scientific publication to prepare the TBS being part of subsequent EU funded projects. An update of the work done will be provided with the D5.7 deliverable (*Additional services updated*) at month M40.

5. ANNEXES

The following User Terms (5.1) and Privacy Policy (5.2) apply to the Meoh App users and will be adapted to mention and include TBS users. The Community Guidelines (5.3) have been co-designed with end-users in workshop #5 in T3.3 and will apply both to TBS and Meoh App users.

5.1 TBS User Terms

Version 1.0

Last revision: 2021/09/09.

Trust Building System (TBS) USER TERMS

MEOH ASBL USER TERMS

By accessing and using the Trust Building System (“**TBS**” or the “**Platform**”), provided by **Meoh ASBL** with registered offices at Rue du Pays de Liège 4, 1000 Brussels, Belgium, and with company number 0599.986.669 (“**Meoh**”, “**we**” or “**us**”), you (“**You**” or the “**User**”) acknowledge that You have read and understand these terms and conditions (the “**User Terms**” or the “**Agreement**”) and You expressly agree with the User Terms as described below.

You agree to enter into a legal binding contract with Meoh. If You do not agree with these User Terms, You will not get access to the Platform. If You want to end the Agreement with Meoh, You can do this at any time by deleting Your account and not using our Platform any longer (by going to My Settings > Delete My Account (see below)).

1. Scope

1.1. Scope

These User Terms govern the contractual relationship between You and Meoh in the context of Your use of the Platform.

You may provide (personal) data and content (e.g. photographs, videos, audios or texts) on the Platform (the “**Content**”). We provide a Platform that enables users on the Platform (the “**Users**”) to communicate with each other and to share that Content.

1.2. Purpose

The purpose of the Platform is for its Users to connect to and engage with reliable partners so that they can support each other.

The object of the User Terms is the use of the Platform for communications (including the sharing of Content) between You and other Users, including the use of other functions made available within the Platform.

1.3. Modifications of the User Terms

Meoh reserves the right to amend the User Terms. In such an event, Meoh will notify You of any material modification of the User Terms, no later than one (1) week before they become effective. If You do not object to the application of the new User Terms, the amended conditions shall be deemed agreed by You. Meoh will inform its Users of the significance of this deadline for objecting separately in the notification containing the amended User Terms and reserves the right to terminate the relationship with the User in the case of an objection.

2. Account

Before using our Platform, You need to register Yourself and create an account (the "**Account**").

In order for You to be eligible to use the Platform, You must:

- a) be at least 17 years old;
- b) have full power and authority to enter into this Agreement and while doing so not violate another agreement in which You are a party; and
- c) only provide truthful information and keep it up to date.

You may request Meoh to delete any of your personal data and/or Content at any time, unless You have shared Your information or Content with other Users on the Platform or to the extent it was used/copied/stored by other Users.

The sale or transfer of an Account on the Platform is not permitted.

2.1. Single Sign-Up

Meoh may provide the User with the option to carry out the Account registration and subsequent sign-in using a single sign-up by accessing the registration data of the User at other providers. If the User chooses this option, Meoh will request the transmission of the User's data from the single sign-up provider selected.

2.2. Account Protection

You must keep Your Account data (such as password) confidential and secure at all times. You must make sure Your Account cannot be accessed by third parties and must immediately notify Meoh via email (to support@meoh.io) in case of any suspicion of unauthorized access. It is prohibited to sell, transfer, lend or trade Your Account or the information on Your Account to or with another party or other Users.

You are liable for Your own activities on the Platform or the activities that take place on Your behalf/with Your Account.

3. Content and communications on the Platform

3.1. Content on the Platform

You can publish Content on your profile page ("**My Profile**") and in the "Communities" section of the platform ("**My Communities**"). Content consists primarily of two types of publications: general announcements or "**Posts**" and private messages or "**Chats**".

Posts and Chats include the original message as well as comments and replies from You and/or other Users. Your Content is available to Your first-degree connections (the "**My Trusted**"), to Users featured by Your Trusted network ("**My Featured**" section), and to members of a Chat group, if you or someone else decides to forward Your Content in a Chat conversation (the "Chat Conversation"). Users having access to the Content through their Newsfeed can repost that Content once, or forward that Content as a private message to other Users in the Chat (a "**Chat Message**").

You may delete Your own Content from Your Profile page by tapping on the trash icon below each publication. You may delete Your Content from Chat Conversations by tapping and holding messages and then tapping on the trash icon. You may choose to delete Your Content in the Chat only for Yourself or for all members of the Chat conversation. Please note that group administrators of a Chat Conversation ("**Admins**") have the ability to delete Chat Messages and Chat Conversations.

Please be aware that You remain responsible for the consequences of sharing, reposting, or forwarding Content with other Users at all times.

3.2. License grant in respect of the Content

"**Intellectual Property Rights**" in these User Terms means any intellectual property rights, including copyrights, trade and service marks, trade names, domain names rights in logos, inventions, trade secrets and know-how, registered designs, design rights, patents, database rights, utility models, all rights of whatsoever nature in computer software and data, any other intellectual and/or industrial property rights all intangible rights and privileges of nature similar or allied to any of the foregoing, in every case in any part of the world and whether or not registered; and including all granted registrations and all applications for registration, all renewals, reversions or extensions, the right to sue for damages for past infringement and all forms of protection of a similar nature which may subsist anywhere in the world.

To the extent You are owner of any Intellectual Property Rights in respect of the Content, You will remain the owner thereof.

Meoh does not have the intention to change or amend the meaning of Your Content. It is however possible that Meoh makes format changes to the Content (e.g. modifying the size).

When posting or providing Content on the Platform, You agree and take knowledge of the fact that Meoh can access, store and process Your Content.

3.3. Conversations on the Platform

All Users invite each other on the Platform through email invitations. All Users can find other second-degree Users (connections of My Trusted) in the network through the 'Featured' section of the Platform.

When sending Chat Messages, please note that:

- a) Private messages are AES encrypted;

- b) User's private key is stored on the User's device and on Our private servers located in Europe; and
- c) Chat group communications ("My Communities") might include Users who are not direct Members of Your Trusted network.

Any rights and obligations following the use of the Platform or the conversations with Users, shall be created exclusively between Users through the exchange of messages.

3.4. Third party rights

You must have the necessary (Intellectual Property) rights to be allowed to upload and use Content. You are responsible for verifying and, if appropriate, acquiring the necessary rights. If You do not own or have obtained the relevant rights, You are not allowed to use such Content on the Platform.

4. Use of the Platform

4.1. Use and availability of the Platform

Under the conditions as set out in these User Terms, Meoh grants the User, when creating his/her Account, a limited, personal, revocable, non-exclusive, non-transferable right to access the Platform (be it through a generally available web browser, mobile device or application). Following this access right, the User is permitted to use the Platform in the way it is made available. Any other use of the Platform, other than as permitted in these User Terms and in Our Community Guidelines, is prohibited.

Meoh cannot guarantee that the Platform will function at any time, continuously without any interruption or that it will work without errors on any electronic device used to gain access to the Platform. Meoh cannot commit itself that the Content placed on the Platform will remain there. However, Meoh will do its best to make Your user experience of the Platform as smooth as possible.

4.2. Software and devices

In order to be able to use the Platform You must provide certain devices, software and data connections Yourself. You consent to manually or automatically download and install updates to Our Platform in order for You to be able to continue to use the Platform.

Please note that while using our Platform, You might access, use or interact with websites, applications or content of third parties. These User Terms only apply to the use of Our Platform. Other third-party websites, applications or content will be governed by their own terms. Meoh cannot be held liable for activities on those third party websites, applications or content.

4.3. Amendments to the Platform and updates

Meoh may make additions or changes to the functions offered in the Platform in order to improve them or adjust them to technical developments (provided that this is reasonable and taking into consideration the interests of the Users and Meoh), but in any case at Meoh's own discretion. In the event that Meoh makes substantial amendments, We will

notify You through our Platform and/or per email about the amendments to be made and about the date of entry into force thereof. Amendments will not work retroactively.

In the event that You disagree with Our (future) amendments, You can terminate Your Agreement with Meoh by deleting Your Account (see clause 9: Termination). In the event You do not delete Your Account, We assume that You agree with the modified User Terms as from the effective date thereof.

Ongoing maintenance and further development may temporarily restrict or interrupt the use of the Platform. No claims against Meoh can be issued in this regard. The User acknowledges that updates to the Platform may be downloaded on the device being used by the User.

4.4. Rules of conduct

4.4.1. Permitted conduct

The Platform may only be used in accordance with these User Terms and Our Community Guidelines.

You must:

- Comply with any applicable laws and regulations relating to Your activities on the Platform;
- Behave respectfully towards other Users on the Platform;
- Abstain from any language that may be perceived as inappropriate or offensive (cfr. clause 4.4.2).

(This is a non-exhaustive list.)

4.4.2. Intolerable conduct

Users will not conduct any communications via the Platform that violate the rights of third parties, contain content that is harmful or extremist content, breach applicable laws, or are deceptive, insulting, pornographic, offensive or glorify violence, or in any other way deemed inappropriate in Meoh's own discretion. In particular, the following conduct is inter alia prohibited ("**Intolerable Conduct**"):

- a) Inappropriate Usernames: any linguistic obscenity, insults, defamations, tackiness, discrimination or abuse in usernames.
- b) Harmful Content: uploading offensive content, any content unsuitable (especially for minors) such as e.g. requests for sexual services.
- c) Insults or Abuse: discrimination, defamation, insults or abuse of individual Users on the grounds of ethnic origin, religion, gender, nationality, sexual orientation or belief.
- d) Harassment of Other Users: sending unrequested messages, chain letters or invitations to participate in sweepstakes.

(This is a non-exhaustive list.)

Intolerable Conduct may result in the User being blocked or, if appropriate, the termination of the Agreement with the User in accordance with clause 9.

It is not allowed to gain access to the Platform or to Content placed on the Platform through scraping, spidering, crawling or other technology or software to access data without the explicit consent of Meoh. It is not permitted to spread viruses, Trojan horses, worms or other malicious content via the Platform or use the Platform if there is a risk that the use could damage technical equipment or software, or in any other way harm the functioning of the Platform.

4.4.3. Identification of Intolerable Conduct.

Users must report or block Intolerable Conduct using the functions available on the Platform (“**Identification**”). This may result in reporting published Content or Users. Report functions are available on each Content publication or on Users’ profile pages (usually by tapping on the 3 vertical dots in the Content or in profile page header). Meoh will do its best efforts to react to such Identification within fourteen (14) business days. Please be aware that a user report of conduct in violation of our User Terms won't necessarily result in us banning the User or otherwise taking action against the User. Meoh filters the current content on the Platform in order to prevent, detect and stop Intolerable Conduct.

4.4.4. Other Illegal Activities and Improper Use.

All Users are prohibited from participating in fraudulent or illegal activities or supporting such activities when using the Platform. In the event of suspected misuse or potential legal infringements (e.g., copyright infringements or infringements of personal rights) on the part of other Users, the User is requested to provide Identification immediately or otherwise send notification to support@meoh.io.

5. Liability of the User

5.1. Liability for the Account

You will remain liable for Your content and Your actions (or on Your behalf) on the Platform.

5.2. Indemnification

To the extent that the User is at fault, the User shall indemnify Meoh against any claims asserted by third parties due to the conduct of the User in connection with the use of the Platform and shall bear the costs incurred for the legal defense according to the statutory fees. In case of any claims asserted by third parties, the User is obligated to provide Meoh immediately, truthfully and completely with all information, which is required for assessing the claims and the defense against such claims.

6. Rights of Meoh

Meoh reserves the right to, in its sole discretion, restrict, suspend (block) or terminate Your Account or Your use of the Platform in the event it is Meoh’s opinion that You misuse or abuse the Platform, any rules of conduct (e.g. Intolerable Conduct or Community Guidelines) or any applicable legislation.

7. Liability of Meoh

7.1. Disclaimer

Meoh does not provide any guarantee whatsoever in respect of the Platform. You agree that You use the Platform at Your own risk. The Platform is provided to You "as is" and based on availability. Meoh does not provide any guarantees in respect of the Platform being uninterrupted or error-free.

To the maximum extent permitted by applicable law, Meoh disclaims any and all warranties, including any implied warranties regarding the Platform or the Content on the Platform.

Meoh cannot guaranty or check the accuracy or correctness of any Content placed on the Platform

7.2. Liability

Meoh will not be held liable for any indirect, incidental or consequential damages (such as without being limited to loss of profit or loss of business opportunities, reputational damage, loss of data) relating to Your use of the Platform.

Meoh will not be liable for any damages in respect or following the User Terms for any amount exceeding the amount of 250 euro. To this extent, Meoh will only be liable for any damage directly caused by breach of the User Terms by Meoh or its subcontractors and to the extent that the damage, error and a causal relationship have been proven.

Meoh is not liable for Your misuse or other Users' misuse of any information or data on the Platform. Unless otherwise stated in these User Terms, Meoh does not control any Content placed on the Platform by its Users nor does it supervise the accounts of Users on the Platform.

The aforementioned exclusions and/or limitations of liability do not apply to Meoh's liability for death, personal injury or for fraud, gross negligence or intentional misconduct.

8. Term

This Agreement shall be valid for an indefinite period.

9. Termination

9.1. Unilateral Termination (Deletion of Your Account)

You can terminate Your Agreement with Meoh at any time and without any reason. You can do so by deleting Your Account on the Platform (by going to the Drop Down Menu > My Settings > Delete My Account). You can also send an e-mail to support@meoh.io to request deletion of Your Account. Upon receipt of such a request, Meoh shall delete your Account within fourteen (14) calendar days.

9.2. Termination by breach of contract or misuse

Meoh reserves the right to terminate Your Account with immediate effect in the event it is Meoh's opinion that You misuse or abuse the Platform or in the event You misbehave towards other Users (cfr. clause 4.4). We may ban Accounts if we believe the Account

activity is in violation of our User Terms. Per our User Terms, we may retain the right to ban You without notification.

9.3. Consequences of termination

After termination of the User Terms, the following provisions will survive:

- Clause 4.4: Rules of Conduct
- Clause 7: Liability
- Clause 11: Intellectual Property Rights
- Clause 12: Governing law and jurisdiction

10. Personal Data and Privacy

Please read Our Privacy Policy²⁴ carefully before using the Platform in order to know more about Meoh processing Your Personal Data.

When You share Your Personal Data on the Platform, You agree with the fact that other Users can view, copy and use this data. Meoh has no control over what Personal Data You share on the Platform, or what other Users may do with it. Meoh is therefore not liable for any dispute or possible damage of any nature whatsoever arising from the sharing or posting of Personal Data on the Platform.

11. Intellectual Property Rights

Meoh will remain the sole and exclusive owner of all right, title and interest in and to all Intellectual Property Rights vested in the Platform, in any form and/or embodiment thereof.

12. Governing law and jurisdiction

These User Terms are governed by the laws of Belgium.

You agree to submit to the exclusive jurisdiction of the competent courts of Brussels, division Brussels.

The United Nations Convention for the International Sale of Goods shall not apply to these User Terms.

13. Miscellaneous

13.1. Notices

The User Terms are provided in English, which language shall be controlling in all respects.

Furthermore, all communications and notices made or given pursuant to the Agreement shall be in the English language.

- Notices by Meoh will be sent to You within the Platform or to the contact details You provided in the Platform (such as email).

²⁴ <https://www.meoh.io/privacy>

- Notices, questions or complaints by You will be sent to Meoh by sending an email to support@meoh.io.

13.2. Entire Agreement

These User Terms contain the entire agreement and understanding between You and Meoh with respect to the subject matter hereof and supersedes and replaces all prior agreements or understandings, whether written or oral, with respect to the same object matter still in force between You and Meoh.

13.3. Transfer of Rights

Meoh is entitled to transfer its rights and obligations resulting from this contractual relationship, in whole or in part, to a third party in observance of a notice period of four (4) weeks, to the extent this is possible.

13.4. Force Majeure

"**Force Majeure Event**" means an event, or a series of related events, that is outside the reasonable control of a party affected (including failures of the internet or any public telecommunications network, hacker attacks or other cyber incidents caused by third parties, denial of service attacks, virus or other malicious software attacks or infections, power failures, epidemics, industrial disputes affecting any third party, social strikes or actions, changes to the law, disasters, explosions, fires, floods, riots, terrorist attacks and wars).

Meoh will not be liable for any delay in performing, or failure to perform, any of its obligations under this Agreement due to a Force Majeure Event. If Meoh refers to a Force Majeure Event, it will immediately inform You of the nature of the Force Majeure Event, stating the date when the Force Majeure Event comes or has come into effect, and also when it will have ceased to exist. In this case, Meoh must use its best efforts to keep the consequences to a minimum.

13.5. Severability

Whenever possible, the provisions of these User Terms shall be interpreted to be valid and enforceable under the applicable law. However, if one or more provisions of these User Terms is found to be invalid, illegal or unenforceable (in whole or in part), the remainder of the provision and of these User Terms shall not be affected and shall continue in full force and effect as if the invalid, illegal or unenforceable provision(s) had never existed. In such case, the Parties shall amend the invalid, illegal or unenforceable provision(s) or any part thereof and/or agree on a new provision, which embodies as closely as possible the purpose of the invalid, illegal or unenforceable provision(s).

5.2 TBS Privacy Policy

Version 1.0

Last revision: 2021/09/09.

TBS PRIVACY POLICY

The protection of your Personal Data and privacy is important to Meoh. Therefore, Meoh wants to inform you as a user of its platform (the “**Platform**”) on how Meoh processes your Personal Data.

All capitalized terms not defined in this Privacy Policy (the “**Privacy Policy**”) will have the meanings as defined in Regulation 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (“**GDPR**”).

1. Who are we?

Meoh ASBL, Rue du Pays de Liège 4, 1000 Brussels, Belgium, hello@meoh.io.

Hereinafter “**Meoh**”, “**we**” or “**us**”.

We qualify as Controller, as defined in the GDPR, with regard to the Processing of your Personal Data for the purposes stated in this Privacy Policy.

2. Which Personal Data do we Process?

As a user of the Platform you can use the Platform to send communications and content to other users. More information on the use of the Platform is to be found in the [User Terms](#).

When you use our Platform, we Process the following sets of Personal Data:

Contact details	Name, surname, email address, an ID assigned to your app-store account, nickname, IP address.
-----------------	---

Personal details and account information	Pictures, texts, images, videos, recordings of the voice or additional information given in the context of transmitted content, password.
Education and work experience	Education, degree, work and job experience.
Technical information	Date and time of your request to access (i.e. visit the app), time zone difference from Greenwich Mean Time (GMT), content of the request (specific site), access status/HTTP status code, volume of data transmitted each time, operating system and its interface, language and the country of origin, status and amount of data transferred, log data.

We Process Your Personal Data when you download the Platform or when you send, post, upload data to our Platform. All information that you post on the Platform and that may contain Personal Data will be Processed by Meoh.

3. The Purposes of the Processing and the legal basis

Below you will find an overview of the purposes and the legal basis of the Personal Data that Meoh Processes. These depend on the category of the Personal Data.

Category	Purpose	Legal basis
Contact details	To use the Platform: to log in to the Platform, to register and to communicate with other users on the Platform. To send you direct marketing [emails and notifications] purposes, for instance to keep you informed about Meoh, its products, promotional offers, events etc. on a monthly basis.	a) Necessary for the performance of the agreement b) Consent c) Soft-opt-in (see article 5)
Technical information	To ensure availability of the Platform.	Necessary for the performance of the agreement

We will inform you in advance, if we intend to Process your Personal Data for purposes other than those specified in this Privacy Policy.

In the event you provided your consent to Meoh, you have the right to withdraw this consent at any time and free of charge. Withdrawal of consent does not affect the Processing of Personal Data (i) prior to such withdrawal, (ii) based on any legitimate ground for Processing Personal Data, and (iii) in case of a legitimate interest in the Processing.

4. The recipients or categories of recipients

We may transfer your Personal Data to affiliated companies, suppliers and service providers, solely in connection with the purposes stated in Article 3 of this Privacy Policy.

Our service providers include, but are not limited to, external IT service providers, marketing agencies, etc.

We may also pass on your Personal Data to third parties if We are required to do so on the basis of legal provisions or decisions of courts.

In the event of a total or partial reorganization or transfer of Our organization, we may also pass on your Personal Data to (un)related third parties.

5. Direct marketing

Meoh may use your Personal Data for direct marketing purposes. In that case, we will ask Your explicit consent for this, but you may withdraw this at any time.

In some cases, sending direct marketing by e-mail or SMS is permitted without your explicit consent, for example because we have obtained your electronic contact details in the context of the sale of products or services and because our commercial messages relate to our similar products or services (“**Soft-opt-in**”).

You may object at any time to further receipt of our direct marketing messages by clicking on “UNSUBSCRIBE”. The unsubscribe option is provided in each direct marketing e-mail. You may also send your intention to unsubscribe by e-mail to unsubscribe@meoh.io.

6. Transfer to a third country or international organization

Your Personal Data will in principle only be processed within the European Economic Area (EEA). In the event that We would transfer your Personal Data to countries outside the EEA, Meoh will ensure that the same level of protection is achieved (e.g. by concluding a standard contractual clause with the Processor located in a country outside the EEA).

7. Retention

Category	Retention period
Contact details	(i) for the entire duration during which you use Our Platform, (ii) for as long as necessary for the aforementioned purposes, or (iii) for as long as We are legally obliged to keep your Personal Data.
Education	(i) for the entire duration during which you use Our Platform, (ii) for as long as necessary for the aforementioned purposes, or (iii) for as long as We are legally obliged to keep your Personal Data.
Technical information	(i) for the entire duration during which you use Our Platform, (ii) for as long as necessary for the aforementioned purposes, or (iii) for as long as We are legally obliged to keep your Personal Data.

8. Your rights

As a Data Subject who's Personal Data are Processed, you have the following rights:

- Right of access to your Personal Data;
- Right to rectification;
- Right to erasure;
- Right to restriction of Processing;
- Right to data portability.

You can exercise the above rights by sending a request by email to privacy@meoh.io.

You also have the right to lodge a complaint with us by sending an email to support@meoh.io. Additionally, you have the right to also lodge a complaint with the Belgian Data Protection Authority (<https://www.dataprotectionauthority.be/>).

9. Applicable law and jurisdiction

The Privacy Policy is governed by the laws of Belgium.

You agree to submit any dispute arising between you and Meoh to the exclusive jurisdiction of the competent courts of Brussels, division Brussels.

10. Changes to the Privacy Policy

We reserve the right to change this Privacy Policy at any time. We will announce any modified version of this Privacy Policy and, where appropriate, request your consent in accordance with the provisions of Article 3 of this Privacy Policy.

DRAFT

5.3 TBS Community Guidelines

After the first practical workshop based on mock-ups to define the ideal cooperation profile for TBS users, we took advantage of the OPERAS-GER national node event²⁵ to devise the Community Guidelines of the TBS following recommendation R.2.6 (See page 97). In October 2021, T.3.5 will start to design the GoTriple Community Guidelines. The TBS Community Guidelines should help inform the GoTriple ones, while making sure that both are aligned.

The objective of the workshop was to co-design the TBS's Community Guidelines, the principles that users agree to abide by when using the TBS, by assessing, challenging, and improving the draft version of the TBS's Community Guidelines.

The main objectives of these Community Guidelines are:

- to keep users safe
- to make sure rules are clear
- to make sanctions justified and easily explainable

We planned to reach the objective of the workshop by preparing an initial draft of the TBS Community Guidelines. Co-designing from these Community Guidelines from scratch would have taken more time than allowed by a 90 minutes workshop. To prepare the draft, we looked for best practices²⁶ and examples²⁷ in the industry. We also looked at existing Community Guidelines, both from the Open Science arena^{28 29 30 31 32} and from well known social media.^{33 34}

From those examples, we identified recurring best practices when it comes to designing Community Guidelines. Those are:

- An introductory paragraph stating the purpose of the community in order to set the tone and to convey a sense of welcoming and interacting without appearing being punitive or scary.

²⁵ <https://operas-ger.hypotheses.org/veranstaltungen/national-node-event#Workshop2>

²⁶ <https://www.communitysignal.com/the-application-of-community-guidelines/>

²⁷ <https://www.webpurify.com/blog/community-guidelines-best-practices-examples/>

²⁸ Humanities Common, <https://hcommons.org/guidelines/>

²⁹ Researchgate.net, <https://www.researchgate.net/community-guidelines>

³⁰ ScienceOpen, <https://cutt.ly/AQd27Qa> & <https://about.scienceopen.com/privacy-policy/>

³¹ Mendeley, <https://www.mendeley.com/terms/>

³² Jstor, <https://about.jstor.org/terms/>

³³ WhatsApp, <https://cutt.ly/eQd9b4R>

³⁴ Lunchclub, <https://cutt.ly/vQd9E9y>

- The style of the Community Guidelines is best to differ from legal and tedious Terms of Services. Community Guidelines must use unambiguous wording, avoid jargon and legalese.
- Community Guidelines must be very easy to locate.

The goal is to get TBS users to actually read guidelines that are easily digestible. Snappy subheadings can help. Bullet points too. We then submitted those draft Community Guidelines to the participants for review and comments. Finally, we used the results of the pre-survey workshop to kickstart the conversation and challenge the initial set of Community Guidelines at the workshop.

TBS Community Guidelines v1.0:

- 1.** Our mission: Our platform is a network committed to help users connect to reliable partners.

In short: Our platform aims to keep all content and interactions professional, constructive, and focused.

1.1. People have the right to understand how to use our platform responsibly, so we have developed these guidelines to help ensure that users have a good experience on the platform. We encourage all users to follow these guidelines when using the platform.

1.2. It is our mission to help our users connect to reliable partners. A big part of successfully connecting people together is the trust people engage while referring someone to somebody.

1.3. We want to make sure that personal discussions on the platform are constructive and that everyone feels free to express their opinions while remaining respectful and tolerant of others.

- 2.** Your personal information.

In short: Be genuine and accurate.

2.1. We encourage our members to use accurate information about themselves. Please do not provide misleading information about your qualifications or work experience, affiliations, or achievements on the platform. You risk losing credibility and negatively impacting the reputation of those who committed their credibility to endorse you.

2.2. While the platform does not maintain a “real name” policy, as a professional oriented network, we ask that your account be associated with your true identity for professional and/or research purposes. Entities such as projects, communities, or organizations are to be represented by a real person.

2.3. We reserve the right to suspend accounts that are not associated with real individuals and real identities, in line with what is described in 2.1 and 2.2.

3. Interacting with other users.

In short: Stay respectful of others and acknowledge diversity.

3.1. Each of our users plays a role in establishing and promoting a positive, inclusive, and encouraging community. Discussions, publications, actions, or comments that promote hatred of any kind are not acceptable through communication on the platform. Members who engage in this kind of behavior expose themselves to be banned either temporarily or permanently from the platform. In the platform User Terms, we explain in more detail your responsibilities when you have an account on our platform, when you post something on your profile, and when you interact with other members.

3.2. The members of our platform engage on the platform to connect and engage with reliable partners. A recommended partner might not always be the right match. We believe that disagreements and healthy debate can lead to great progress. To facilitate these important conversations, we ask that our members respect each other's ideas and acknowledge the diversity of thought and opinion.

3.3. Harassment, defamatory and derogatory comments, explicit comments and content, and hate speech will not be tolerated. This includes personal attacks and attacks on other people based on their:

- Race, ethnicity or national origin
- Political or religious affiliation
- Sexual orientation, gender or gender identity
- Age, serious disease, or disability

3.4. This can be a delicate balancing act, but here intention is key; if the primary purpose is to attack, the content crosses the line.

3.5. Please note: members who repeatedly engage in disrespectful behavior risk having their content reported, deleted, and their membership disabled.

4. Best practices

In short: The following best practices outline our expectations for appropriate online behavior for all users.

4.1. What to do:

- Be courteous and respectful. Respect one another's privacy and intellectual property.
- Stay on topic. Limit all discussions to professionally relevant topics.
- Respect people's choices: If you add someone to a group and they remove themselves, please honor that decision.
- Try to not use jargon to ease mutual understanding and improve chances of cooperation
- Treat TBS introductions like you would treat introductions from a friend or a trusted colleague. Respond in a timely manner to the introduction message, and communicate in a friendly and professional way.

4.2. What not to do:

- Violate our Terms of Service: As a reminder, the Terms of Service define your contractual relationship with our platform and the Terms of Service take precedence to the extent there is any conflict with this document.
- Do not post inflammatory, derogatory, or otherwise inappropriate comments about other users (see section 3).
- Do not promote, condone, or encourage illegal activity in your postings.

5. Inappropriate content and behaviours

In short: Our platform's support team takes every report of hatred, violence, and harassment seriously. We encourage everyone to act and interact responsibly.

5.1. We prioritize working with those affected by inappropriate content to determine what the next steps should be - the safety of our users is of utmost importance. If you have been subject to any of the inappropriate behaviours or content suggested at the above point 3 "Interacting with other users" please refer to [URL link to be inserted] for in-depth guidelines on how to report content or people.

5.2. Our support team will review reported content, remove it if necessary, and take further action if needed. Users found to have broken our platform Terms of Services, Privacy Policy, and/or Community Guidelines might be banned temporarily or indefinitely from the platform.

5.4 TBS User Profiles

Following three theoretical workshops which allowed us to grasp the essence of what a TBS could be through discussions around (a) the Needs & Purpose, (b) the Values & Principles, and (c) the Stakeholders and their preferred Feedback Loops, we decided to translate end-users' recommendations as mock-up designs.

We started off by designing cooperation profiles. A cooperation profile is meant to enhance basic user profiles with information that will better help TBS users connect to reliable partners. We also asked participants to provide us with information they would find meaningful in the frame of EU-funded projects. To do so, we looked at related outputs from the previous three workshops for inspiration:

- “How to be user friendly and attractive to those outside our usual social circles/discipline?” (R.1.1 - D3.3).
- “How to best convey a “human touch” to the user profile?” (Following R.3.4 - D3.3).
- “How to introduce trusted contacts to one another?” (Following R3.5 - D3.3).

Based on the workshop results, we drafted an updated version of the existing basic user profiles with participants' recommendations, bearing in mind that the technological, graphic, budgetary and user-friendly parameters would first need to be discussed with the Task 5.3 developers.

TABLE 4: Summary of recommendations (R.4) from Workshop #4 in Task 3.3.

<p>In black: pre-workshop draft In blue: workshop recommendations for TRIPLE Task 5.3</p>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. My username 2. My location <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. City b. Country 3. Work <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Position b. Organisation c. My needs d. My expertise (e.g. communication skills) e. Shared interest (Detected by Artificial Intelligence?) f. Achievements/References to previous work/outcomes/project results/impact evaluation/testimonies (award page?)

- a. EU projects related
 - i. Involvement in past/current/future EU projects
 - ii. Experience as EU projects's participant or leader
 - iii. Experience as EU project's coordinator
 - iv. Resources to write a proposal or lead a WP
- 4. About me
 - a. Professional mission & vision; Work style; Learning style
 - b. Current topic of interest / what the person is looking for
 - c. What do you like in life? What is your dream?
 - d. What is your most recent belief update? (something you used to think of in a way that has now changed/transitioned/evolved)
- 2. Why I'm here: tell others what drives you forward
 - a. Shared values and work ethic, fair-play of the person
 - b. Side projects I'm working on
 - c. Stuff I'm interested in/I would like to learn about
- 3. Education
 - a. Field of study
 - b. Degree
 - c. School
- 4. Social
 - a. Website
 - b. Social profile

6. REFERENCES

- [1] Weyenbergh, G.V., Werner, B., 2018. A Social Architecture to Scale Trust, Steps Towards a Social Ecosystem. *Meoh Working Paper*.
- [2] Bouillard, M. et al., *D3.3: Report on the Trust Building System User Design Research*, TRIPLE, 2021.
- [3] Di Donato, F. et al., *D6.2: Report on Procedure to follow to be part of the EOSC Catalogue*, TRIPLE, 2021.

DRAFT